

ISic0606

I.Sicily inscription 0606

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

urn

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Seen by Gualtherus either near the city gate, or in the doorway of the church of San Bartolomeo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus)

2. Munatiae

3. Paullae

4. Laternina

5. Quinta matri

6. piissimae

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491871

EDR 159457
EDCS 22100610
PHI 334881

Bibliography

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